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RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	Effect Characterization of Proton Radiation on LEAP OBТ (ECPRL)
Project TA identifier	TA10-314
General application	Datacom, harsh environments, space, aviation, physics research, medical
Type of test	TNID
Group leader, Institute	Matthias Hendel, Amphenol AOP
Co-authors, Institutes	Mathias-Emanuel Hartmann, Dirk Bettermann, Alexandre Lassalle. All Amphenol AOP
Date(s) of the experiment	2025-03-24 to 2025-03-26
Facility	Paul Scherrer Institut
Amount of access granted (unit of access: 1h)	11

Objectives of the experiments

The objective of this experiment was to characterize the effects of proton radiation on a state-of-the-art optical transceiver for harsh environments. The tested transceiver was Amphenol Active Optical Products' QEPT Module. This deviation from the initially proposed LEAP OBТ was initiated after talking to the RADNEXT TA Team, when SEE tests performed by CNES/TRAD in Q4 2024 indicated, that the LEAP OBТ was susceptible to single event effects.

The initial testing was performed between the 24th and the 26th of March 2025 at the Paul Scherrer Institute in Switzerland. The full analysis of the test results is still ongoing and will be completed after the irradiated samples are released from quarantine. This is currently expected to happen towards the backend of 2025.

Non the less, the preliminary results presented in this report already provide some valuable insight into the robustness of the QEPT with regards to displacement damage and represent a significant step towards having a fully radiation characterized, European manufactured, COTS optical transceiver.

<https://radnext.web.cern.ch/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/radnext>

Figure 1: Amphenol AOP QEPT Module

Experiment test report

All Results are considered preliminary.

A total of 14 of Amphenol AOPs QEPT modules were exposed, in three batches, to varying fluences of a 50-MeV Proton beam. The samples were grouped in batches of 6 units, which were placed in the beam at the same time.

Batch composition Table		Day 1		Day 2		note
Serial Numbers	Part Number	Batch	Position	Batch	Position	
QA2509-00008	TR252041PMTA1C00	1	1	3	1	
QA2509-00013	TR252041PMTA1C00	1	2	x	x	
QA2509-00009	TR252041PMTA1C00	1	3	x	x	
QA2509-00005	TR252041PMTA1C00	1	4	x	x	
QA2509-00007	TR252041PMTA1C00	1	5	3	5	
QA2452-00008	TR252041PMTA1C0S	1	6	3	6	"space" configuration
QA2509-00010	TR252041PMTA1C00	2	1	x	x	
QB2504-00001	TR252041PMTA1C0S	2	2	3	2	"space" configuration
QA2509-00006	TR252041PMTA1C00	2	3	x	x	
QA2509-00004	TR252041PMTA1C00	2	4	x	x	
QA2509-00001	TR252041PMTA1C00	2	5	x	x	
QA2509-00002	TR252041PMTA1C00	2	6	x	x	
QA2509-00014	TR252041PMTA1C00	Control				
QA2509-00003	TR252041PMTA1C00	x	x	3	3	
QA2509-00012	TR252041PMTA1C00	x	x	3	4	

The samples were biased according to the following schematic:

Figure 2: Bias Configuration During Irradiation

Due to the sample distribution on the test board (see below) the fluence distribution was not uniform within one Batch

Figure 3: QEPT DD Testfixture Top View

To account for the heterogenous distribution the calibration data was interpolated into an adjustment factor, reflecting both the beam calibration data as well as the modules position on the board. Both this adjustment factor, as well as the fluences (per tests and accumulated) may be found in the following table.

Fluence per Test/Module

Batch 1	T1		T2		T3		T4		Position	adjustment Factor
	Test	Accumulated	Test	Accumulated	Test	Accumulated	Test	Accumulated		
nominal Fluence	5.52E+09	5.52E+09	5.55E+09	1.11E+10	4.40E+10	5.51E+10	5.50E+10	1.10E+11		
adjusted Fluences:										
QA2509-00008	5.12E+09	5.12E+09	5.15E+09	1.03E+10	4.09E+10	5.11E+10	5.11E+10	1.02E+11	1	0.928302689
QA2509-00013	5.33E+09	5.33E+09	5.36E+09	1.07E+10	4.25E+10	5.32E+10	5.32E+10	1.06E+11	2	0.966366219
QA2509-00009	4.56E+09	4.56E+09	4.58E+09	9.14E+09	3.63E+10	4.55E+10	4.54E+10	9.09E+10	3	0.825904515
QA2509-00005	3.73E+09	3.73E+09	3.75E+09	7.47E+09	2.97E+10	3.72E+10	3.71E+10	7.43E+10	4	0.67531594
QA2509-00007	3.58E+09	3.58E+09	3.60E+09	7.19E+09	2.86E+10	3.58E+10	3.57E+10	7.15E+10	5	0.649545396
QA2452-00008	4.13E+09	4.13E+09	4.15E+09	8.28E+09	3.29E+10	4.12E+10	4.12E+10	8.23E+10	6	0.748047762

Fluence per Test

Batch 2	T1		T2		T3		T4		Position	adjustment Factor
	Test	Accumulated	Test	Accumulated	Test	Accumulated	Test	Accumulated		
nominal Fluence	8.92E+10	8.92E+10	9.48E+10	1.84E+11	8.79E+10	2.72E+11	1.09E+11	3.81E+11		
adjusted Fluences:										
QA2509-00010	8.28E+10	8.28E+10	8.80E+10	1.71E+11	8.16E+10	2.52E+11	1.01E+11	3.53E+11	1	0.928302689
QB2504-00001	8.62E+10	8.62E+10	9.17E+10	1.78E+11	8.49E+10	2.63E+11	1.05E+11	3.68E+11	2	0.966366219
QA2509-00006	7.37E+10	7.37E+10	7.83E+10	1.52E+11	7.26E+10	2.25E+11	8.97E+10	3.14E+11	3	0.825904515
QA2509-00004	6.02E+10	6.02E+10	6.40E+10	1.24E+11	5.93E+10	1.84E+11	7.33E+10	2.57E+11	4	0.67531594
QA2509-00001	5.79E+10	5.79E+10	6.16E+10	1.20E+11	5.71E+10	1.77E+11	7.05E+10	2.47E+11	5	0.649545396
QA2509-00002	6.67E+10	6.67E+10	7.09E+10	1.38E+11	6.57E+10	2.03E+11	8.12E+10	2.85E+11	6	0.748047762

Batch 3	Fluence per Test						Position	
	T1		T2		T3			
	Test	Accumulated	Test	Accumulated	Test	Accumulated		
nominal Fluence	1.90E+11	1.90E+11	1.90E+11	3.80E+11	1.30E+11	5.10E+11		
adjusted Fluences:								
QA2509-00008	1.76E+11	1.76E+11	1.76E+11	3.53E+11	1.21E+11	4.73E+11	1	0.928302689
QB2504-00001	1.84E+11	1.84E+11	1.84E+11	3.67E+11	1.26E+11	4.93E+11	2	0.966366219
QA2509-00003	1.57E+11	1.57E+11	1.57E+11	3.14E+11	1.07E+11	4.21E+11	3	0.825904515
QA2509-00012	1.28E+11	1.28E+11	1.28E+11	2.57E+11	8.78E+10	3.44E+11	4	0.67531594
QA2509-00007	1.23E+11	1.23E+11	1.23E+11	2.47E+11	8.44E+10	3.31E+11	5	0.649545396
QA2452-00008	1.42E+11	1.42E+11	1.42E+11	2.84E+11	9.72E+10	3.82E+11	6	0.748047762

Module not functional: red, module impacted but functional: yellow. Module functional: green. "space" module variant in blue text

Generally, as indicated by the colour coding in the preceding table, the two transceivers QA2452-00008 and QB2504-00001 survived irradiation in excess of 3.82E11 particles per square cm with minor, non functional effects. Both of these parts are prototypes of the "Space" version of the QEPT. Non of the other parts survived more than 1.38E11 with the first parts failing after 3.72E10 particles per square cm.

Since the objective of this experiment was to characterize the behaviour of the QEPT with regards to displacement damage, the project may already be considered a success based on these preliminary findings alone. Release of the completed report depends on the completion of two additional tasks.

Firstly, a number of parameters were measured after every irradiation step and are currently being analysed regarding their fluence dependent changes.

Secondly, a final set of measurements is to be performed on the modules, once they clear quarantine at PSI. The next chance for this is currently anticipated in December 2025.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	X

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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